

AI in TESOL: How Artificial Intelligence Is Transforming the Role of the Teacher

Abstract

Since ChatGPT appeared in 2022, the topic of AI in education has become very active worldwide, with debates about limiting its use or including it as part of the learning process (Bower et al., 2025).

However, leading researchers and practitioners agree that AI will not replace teachers, but teachers who effectively use AI will replace those who do not (Nikitina & Ishchenko, 2024; Devika, 2025).

Teachers now face new expectations and opportunities. This paper explores the concept of *AI literacy* as a new professional competence for TESOL (Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages) teachers. Drawing on recent research and frameworks, it analyses what AI literacy means, why it is important, and how teachers can develop it through professional training and reflective practice. The review shows that AI literacy combines technical, pedagogical, and ethical skills that help teachers use AI meaningfully in English language classrooms.

Keywords:

Artificial Intelligence (AI), TESOL, AI literacy, teacher education, human-centred learning, digital competence

Introduction

In recent years, international organisations (UNESCO, 2023; TESOL International Association, 2023) and government agencies (Australian Government, 2024; NSW Department of Education, 2025) have been formulating strategies for integrating AI into the educational environment with an emphasis on human-centred AI—technologies that enhance, rather than replace, human interaction. Recent Australian frameworks — AI in Australian Education Snapshot (ESA, 2023) and the AI in Education Framework (2024) — also stress the same idea. They highlight three main goals:

1. keeping the teacher at the centre of the learning process (human-in-the-loop)
2. developing AI literacy among teachers
3. ensuring the ethical and responsible use of AI in schools.

This paper critically analyses scholarly and policy literature on how AI transforms the teacher's role in English language education. How is the integration of artificial intelligence transforming the role of the teacher in language education, and what pedagogical implications does this have for TESOL practice?

This review offers ideas and guidance for English language teachers who want to use AI meaningfully. It focuses on the pedagogical and ethical competencies that help teachers stay central in the learning process while working with AI tools.

The Global Debate about AI in Education

In Australia, people started to talk about artificial intelligence in schools and universities after ChatGPT appeared. At first, schools were worried about cheating and losing academic honesty. Universities, such as Curtin, made their own rules about using or banning generative AI tools. It is also important to note that these AI policies are constantly changing and being updated. Policies now regulate how generative AI can be used for assignments and learning. The Appropriate Use of GenAI Technologies (Curtin University, n.d.) encourages AI tools' ethical and transparent application rather than banning them.

The Australian Framework for Generative AI in Schools report (Australian Government, 2024) emphasises that the goal is to assist teachers, not replace them. AI should take over routine tasks—test marking, data collection, planning—so teachers have more time to interact with

students. The NSW Department of Education (2025) adds that it is important for teachers to develop AI literacy—the ability to understand, analyse, and use technology effectively.

UNESCO (2023) makes a similar point: technology should be "human-centred, inclusive, equitable, and ethical," that is, serving people and empowering them.

In Russia, the position aligns with the international one: AI can assist, but should not replace humans. Education Minister Sergei Kravtsov has repeatedly emphasised: "Artificial intelligence will never replace teachers, but it can make their work easier". In China, new AI literacy lessons were recently announced for schools. Effective 1 September 2025, China made AI training mandatory in primary and secondary schools: a minimum of eight hours of AI training per year for students (TASS, 2025; RIA Novosti, 2024).

In Singapore, teachers are taking courses on integrating AI tools into English, mathematics, and science instruction. For example, in the SkillsFuture for Educators project, teachers learn ChatGPT, Grammarly, and multimodal content generators as part of their professional development. Researchers Tan & Lim (2024) emphasise that Singapore emphasises the ethical and conscious use of technology to preserve the humanistic nature of education.

Researchers confirm that fear gradually gives way to the understanding that AI is a new pedagogical assistant.

Opportunities and Challenges of Implementing AI in English Language Teaching: A Literature Review

The studies show that artificial intelligence is changing English teaching. In many places - from big TESOL reports (TESOL, 2023) to real classrooms (Song, 2024; Ulla & Teng, 2024) researchers say that AI can make lessons better, but do not replace the teacher (Australian Government Department of Education, 2024; Bower et al., 2025; Devika, 2025; New South Wales Department of Education, 2025; Nikitina & Ishchenko, 2024; Ulla & Teng, 2024; Song, 2024; Tu, 2024; Yulianti, 2023; Vishnu Ambedkar & Thakar, 2025; Bangulzai et al., 2025). The research can be divided into three main topics.

1. AI as a Support Tool, not a Replacement
2. Ethical and Social Challenges
3. Teacher Training and AI Literacy

AI as a Support Tool, not a Replacement

In many studies, researchers agree that AI should help teachers in their work, not replace them (ESA, 2023; Ulla & Teng, 2024; Song, 2024; Yulianti, 2025; Devika, 2025; Daud et al., 2025).

ESA (2023) explains that teachers must stay in control of how AI is used — this is called *human oversight*. The AI Framework (2024) uses a similar idea, calling it *human-in-the-loop*. The AI Framework (2024) provides a global overview of policies and research directions, while Song (2024) and Yulianti (2025) show how these ideas work in real classroom situations.

Ulla and Teng (2024) explore how generative AI can support English teaching, discussing its benefits, challenges, and future possibilities.

The authors analyse how generative AI can facilitate the creation of adaptive and personalised learning materials, provide rapid and relevant feedback, and stimulate student creativity. Particular attention is paid to the impact of AI on reducing anxiety in language learning and the potential for developing creativity in learners.

The review Daud et al. (2025) shows that AI supports English language teaching in many ways, such as grammar checkers, chatbots, and language learning apps. The most common use is for writing practice and feedback. The study also finds that AI helps to personalise learning, improve student motivation, and make administrative work more comfortable.

Yulianti (2025) emphasises similar ideas, noting that artificial intelligence should not be seen as a substitute for teachers but as an assistant that makes learning more flexible, accessible, and personalised. She also writes that AI helps give feedback and language practice, but cannot do what teachers do — understand emotions, communicate with students, and help them think deeply. This idea is also supported by Devika (2025), who says that AI and teachers should work together as partners in education, not replace each other.

Song (2024) demonstrates how these ideas work in practice in a real-world TESOL environment. The project involves teachers from China and South Africa with different linguistic and cultural backgrounds (Song, 2024).

The aim was to see how teachers use AI in their lessons, what help they need, and how they can teach better. These tools included ChatGPT to make dialogues and writing ideas, Grammarly to check writing and give feedback, and AI learning systems to see students' progress

and change tasks for them. Speech tools helped students practise pronunciation, and AI reports showed teachers how well students were learning and participating in class.

The project showed that AI works best when teachers actively co-create and reflect on how to use it. Instead of replacing teachers, AI became a teaching partner, helping to reduce routine tasks, personalise learning, and make lessons more interactive. The study highlights that successful AI integration in TESOL depends on technology and teachers' understanding, collaboration, and ability to design meaningful AI-supported activities (Song, 2024).

Ethical and Social Challenges

Several studies raise concerns about data privacy, algorithmic bias, and unequal access to AI tools (TESOL, 2023; Ulla & Teng, 2024; Kohnke et al., 2025; Daud et al., 2025).

The Research Directions Working Group of the TESOL International Association wrote the article TESOL Research Directions 2023–2027. It combines information from surveys and focus groups with more than 600 teachers, researchers, and education professionals from different countries.

The article identifies four key research areas: developing research literacy and education; professional development for all participants in the educational process; studying effective teaching methods; and integrating new educational technologies, including artificial intelligence.

The article emphasises the emergence of AI as an integral tool for modernising the educational process, facilitating personalised learning, automated assessment, providing intelligent support to teachers, and expanding access to resources.

The article highlights that we must look carefully at ethical and social issues when using AI, including data protection, unfair algorithms, and the danger of making education less equal.

Ulla and Teng (2024) also discuss some problems, like the risk of technology addiction, challenges with academic honesty, privacy concerns, and ethical questions from using AI in education. These problems show that teachers need to use AI carefully and rationally in TESOL.

Daud et al. (2025) also show some problems with AI in education. These include cheating, overusing technology, language issues, and technical limits. The report says teachers need special training to use AI tools ethically and effectively.

While Yulianti (2025) stresses emotional dimensions of teaching, Kohnke & Zou (2025) focus on the cognitive integration of AI tools, suggesting that teacher readiness must encompass both emotional and technological literacies.

Kohnke et al.(2025) also note that AI is imperfect. It often reflects a single culture or language and may not account for student differences. Therefore, teachers must be mindful when teaching students to think critically about AI and understand its limitation. It is also important for teachers to learn how to use AI technically and ethically- to protect student data and ensure academic integrity (Kohnke et al., 2025).

The integration of AI should ensure the equitable participation of all stakeholders in the educational process (Australian Government, 2024).

Teacher Training and AI Literacy

Helping teachers understand how to use AI is one of the main challenges in many studies (TESOL International Association, 2023; Kohnke et al., 2025; Song, 2024). Both theory and real classroom projects show that teachers need ongoing training to use AI carefully, fairly, and correctly. ESA (2023) and the Framework (2024) describe AI literacy as an important skill for teachers. Kohnke and Zou (2025) connect this with the TPACK and SAMR models, showing how teachers can learn to use technology and pedagogy together.

TESOL emphasises that teachers should not simply master new tools but also learn to use technology consciously in the classroom. This includes "AI literacy" skills - understanding when and why to use artificial intelligence. Importantly, this is not a technical skill in Australia, but a new educational competency, part of general digital literacy (Australian Government, 2024).

The report also mentions the need to train teachers to use AI effectively through better digital and research literacy (TESOL, 2023). The article highlights that we must look carefully at ethical and social issues when using AI, including data protection, unfair algorithms, and the danger of making education less equal. The report also mentions the need to train teachers to use AI effectively through better digital and research literacy.

By the end of the Song experiment, participants were able to develop their first new ideas for using AI best to improve student motivation and academic performance. However, it was clear that AI does not replace teachers, but rather supports them, and for this to happen, teachers

themselves must participate in the development and adaptation of technologies. Similar ideas can also be seen in the work of Bangulzai, A. R., Begum, R., Mirza, M., and Ahmad, S. (2025).

The article shows the real advantages and problems teachers have when they start using AI. It explains that success depends on the technology and how teachers understand and use it in different cultures and classrooms (Song, 2024).

The work of Song (2024) goes well together with the ideas of Kohnke et al. (2025). Song shows real examples of how teachers use AI and what problems they face, while Kohnke et al. explain, with the TPACK and SAMR models, how teachers can plan and use AI in a more effective way.

Thus, Kohnke's model explains Song's practical observations, and the proposed framework helps us understand how to develop teachers' digital and pedagogical literacy systemically.

The article uses two simple models - TPACK and SAMR - to explain how teachers can use technology in a smarter way.

The TPACK model helps explain what teachers need to know to use technology well. It combines three main areas of knowledge:

Subject knowledge - what teachers know about their subject (for example, English).

Pedagogical knowledge - how to teach and help students learn effectively.

Technological knowledge - using tools like AI and other digital technologies in lessons.

When teachers connect all three, they can use technology smartly and meaningfully, supporting teaching and learning (Kohnke et al., 2025).

The second model, SAMR, explains how technology changes the learning process:

Substitution - simply replacing an old tool with a new one, without changing the essence.

Augmentation - technology helps achieve the same thing, but more conveniently.

Modification -changing the learning process itself, adding new capabilities.

Redefinition - a new way of learning is emerging that was previously impossible.

The article demonstrates that teachers must strive beyond replacement and enhancement, implementing technologies to transform and improve learning (Kohnke et al., 2025).

Pedagogical Transformation and New Teacher Roles

The reviewed literature shows that teachers are no longer just people who give knowledge. Now they become designers of learning and guides for using technology.

According to TESOL Research Directions 2023–2027, teachers need to build AI literacy — to understand what AI can do, when to use it, and when not to. Teachers should also learn to think critically about technology, not just follow it. The Framework (2024) says teachers should know how to use AI to make lessons more personal and flexible. The Framework (2024) also includes governance and risk management.

This shift in the teacher’s role aligns with general principles of effective language pedagogy. Richards and Rodgers (2014) explain that language teachers should act as facilitators who guide students to communicate meaningfully rather than transmit knowledge.

AI can support teachers in the classroom (Ulla & Teng, 2024). For example, it can check grammar, give comments, or help students practise pronunciation. However, only teachers can explain mistakes, guide discussions, and motivate students to improve. This idea is also shared by Tu (2024), who highlights that AI can assist teachers in improving learning outcomes.

In the study by Song (2024), they learned that AI works best when teachers help to design activities and reflect on how to use it. When teachers take part in creating lessons with AI, it becomes a real learning tool.

Daud et al. (2025) said teachers must ensure that AI helps everyone, not just some students. They also make decisions about what is right and safe to use AI.

However, many problems still exist. Many teachers do not feel ready or trained to use AI well. Song (2024) and Kohnke et al. (2025) show that teachers need more time and support to learn how to use AI in lessons. Some teachers worry that technology can make lessons less human or reduce student communication.

Kohnke et al. (2025) suggest that teacher training should include three kinds of knowledge: technology, pedagogy, and subject (the TPACK model). Teachers should learn to use AI tools carefully, adapt them to their students, and keep real human contact in every lesson.

They also describe the SAMR model, which shows different levels of using technology in teaching.

This idea matches the Australian Framework for Generative AI in Schools (Australian Government, 2024), which says that the teacher should stay the main person in the classroom.

All studies also agree that teachers need to keep learning and growing. They should take part in training and share their experience with other teachers.

Trends, Implications, and Gaps in the Research

Trends

Across the reviewed papers, some main ideas are the same.

First, many researchers say that AI should help teachers, not take their place (ESA, 2023; Devika, 2025; Yulianti, 2025).

Second, teachers need to know how to use AI — it is now an important skill (TESOL, 2023; Kohnke & Zou, 2025; Song, 2024).

Third, researchers say that schools should use AI in a careful and responsible way (UNESCO, 2023; Australian Government, 2024).

Finally, the teacher's job is changing — teachers are not only giving knowledge now, but also guiding students (Song, 2024; Kohnke & Zou, 2025).

Implications

Teachers must learn not only how to use AI tools technically but also how to integrate them into pedagogy in meaningful ways.

Teacher education programs should include AI literacy, critical thinking about technology, and classroom design using models such as TPACK and SAMR (Kohnke & Zou, 2025).

Professional collaboration and continuous learning are necessary to keep AI implementation ethical, inclusive, and effective across different teaching contexts.

Gaps

However, several gaps remain.

There is little empirical research on how AI affects teacher–student interaction and feedback quality in language classrooms.

Few studies examine students' emotional engagement or cultural differences in AI-supported TESOL settings.

Also, most research focuses on higher education, while primary and secondary school contexts remain underexplored.

Finally, current studies rarely investigate long-term outcomes of AI use in developing learners' communicative competence.

These gaps show the need for more classroom-based research to understand how AI can enhance learning without losing the human connection.

Conclusion

This review shows that AI literacy is becoming an important skill for TESOL teachers. As Artificial Intelligence is used more in education, teachers need to know how to use it to help learning, not to replace real human interaction. The studies in this review also show that teachers must find a balance between using new technology and following ethical principles. Teachers should be able to evaluate AI tools critically, integrate them into lessons through models such as SAMR and TPACK, and maintain attention to cultural and emotional aspects of learning.

Developing AI literacy helps teachers design more flexible and creative learning experiences while keeping students' needs and human connection at the centre.

References

- Australian Institute of Higher Education. (2024). *Artificial intelligence in education (AIED) framework*.
- Australian Government Department of Education. (2024). *2024 review of the Australian framework for generative artificial intelligence in schools*. National AI in Schools Taskforce.
- Bangulzai, A. R., Begum, R., Mirza, M., & Ahmad, S. (2025). The future of teaching: Examining the role of AI tutors and human teachers in co-teaching models. *The Critical Review of Social Sciences Studies*, 3(3), 813–829.
- Curtin University. (n.d.). *Appropriate use of GenAI technologies*. Retrieved October 5, 2025, from <https://www.curtin.edu.au/students/essentials/rights/academic-integrity/gen-ai/>
- Daud, A., Aulia, A. F., Muryanti, Harfal, Z., Nabilla, O., & Ali, H. S. (2025). Integrating artificial intelligence into English language teaching: A systematic review. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 14(2), 677–691.
<https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.14.2.677>
- Devika, K. H. (2025). AI & teachers: Partners in education, not replacements. *International Journal of Latest Technology in Engineering, Management & Applied Science*, 14(4), 678–685. <https://doi.org/10.51583/IJLTEMAS.2025.140400077>
- Education Services Australia (ESA). (2023). *AI in Australian education snapshot: Principles, policy, and practice*. Education Services Australia.
- Kohnke, L., & Zou, D. (2025). Artificial intelligence integration in TESOL teacher education: Promoting a critical lens guided by TPACK and SAMR. *TESOL Quarterly*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.3396>
- New South Wales Department of Education. (2025, September 22). *Artificial intelligence in education*. <https://education.nsw.gov.au/teaching-and-learning/education-for-a-changing-world/artificial-intelligence-in-education>

- Nikitina, I., & Ishchenko, T. (2024). The impact of AI on teachers: Support or replacement? *Journal of Pedagogical Innovations*, 5(2), 45–54.
- Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2014). *Approaches and methods in language teaching* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Song, Y. (2024). Co-creating blended teaching activities using AI in TESOL contexts: Report of an online Change Laboratory pilot study. *TESOL Journal*.
<https://doi.org/10.71957/scy10g84>
- Tan, C., & Lim, J. (2024). *Ethical integration of AI tools in Singaporean classrooms*. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Education and Technology*, 42(2), 156–170.
- TESOL International Association Research Professional Council. (2023). *TESOL research directions 2023–2027*. TESOL International Association. <https://www.tesol.org>
- Tu, L. (2024). The future of teaching: Examining the role of AI. *International Journal of Education and Technology Studies*.
- Ulla, M. B., & Teng, M. F. (2024). Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications in TESOL: Opportunities, issues, and perspectives. *International TESOL Union Journal*.
<https://www.tesolunion.org/journal/details/info/1Mjc52LjFk/>
- UNESCO. (2023). *Final 2023 recommendations: How we got here*. UNESCO.
- Yulianti, S. (2023). Can AI replace teachers in English language learning? *Tanjungpura University Journal of English Language Education*, 4(2).
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/388921348>